

Comparative Analysis of Convolutional Neural Networks and Principal Component Analysis for CT and MRI Brain Image Fusion: Enhancing Diagnostic Accuracy and Visualization

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Abstract

Medical image fusion is used for combining complementary information from various imaging modalities that can help in disease diagnosis and treatment planning. This research work presents a comparative image fusion algorithm between Computed Tomography (CT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) brain images using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). The final fused CT-MRI images contain the CT structural details and MRI soft tissue contrast. The fusion process is improved by training the CNN to refine the PCA-fused images by learning the optimal feature extraction and combination through multiple convolutional layers. The aim of using CNN is to enhance the clarity, reduce noise, also preserve information in the fused images. The proposed work is analysed with a CT-MRI dataset obtained from Kaggle and qualitative metrics such as Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), entropy, and correlation coefficient. Research findings indicate that multimodal CNN image fusion considerably performs better than multimodal image fusion using PCA. Higher values of SSIM, PSNR obtained in CNN-based image fusion indicates improved structural similarity and less noise. The increased values of entropy, correlation coefficients and visual assessments also aid in favour with our study.

Keywords— Medical Image Fusion, Multi model Brain images Computed Tomography Magnetic Resonance Imaging, Disease diagnosis, Treatment planning, PCA based image fusion, Convolutional Neural Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Combining images from multiple modalities into a single composite image that contains more information is image fusion, and it is widely used in many arenas including medicine. [2]. The main aim of medical image fusion is to enhance the image clarity which favours the disease diagnosis and treatment [3]. CT and MRI imaging modalities of brain are the most popular imaging modalities that is critically used in disease detection, diagnosis [23]. In addition to managing neurological conditions like tumors, strokes, and traumatic brain injuries [24]. CT, known for its detailed bone structure imaging, and MRI, recognized for its superior soft tissue contrast.

When CT and MRI brain images are fused, the details present in CT and MRI are combined and offers a detailed view in a single image that provides improved accuracy in diagnosis, better treatment planning and patient monitoring. Image fusion algorithms are broadly grouped into 1. Spatial domain fusion 2. Frequency domain or multi-scale decomposition 3. Machine Learning [4]. Though Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a dimension reduction statistical technique, it can be used in image fusion to captures the most considerable features through decomposition from the input source images [26]. PCA transforms the CT and MRI images into a set of principal components that encapsulate the most substantial variations in the data [4]. CNN can extract complex features from large datasets [28], and hence plays a vital role in the image fusion process. In this proposed work, CNN is used to fuse CT and MRI images which potentially outperforms existing techniques.

The proposed work also performs a detailed comparative review on CNN based CT-MRI brain image fusion and PCA based CT-MRI brain image fusion. The main goal of this research work is to determine the most effective algorithm for the final fused image that contains the details of CT and MRI information for better diagnosis, accuracy, visualization and better treatment planning.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jingjiang Xu et. al. presented a PCA-based image fusion algorithm for skin burn detection which improves visualization in polarization-sensitive OCT. The drawback of the proposed method included sensitivity loss and interpretation difficulty [1]. Mojtaba Safari et. al. put forward a MedFusionGAN, the algorithm fuses CT image with MRI images. However misaligned input images required further validation [6]. Leonardo Acho et. al. presented a combination of slicing image transformation with PCA for image fusion which enhanced the image quality but the limitation included requirement of diverse dataset [7]. Balakrishnan et al. came up with a VoxelMorph algorithm for image fusion that used CNN for image registration [8]. Jinxin Wang et al. presented a complex image fusion algorithm for combining infrared and visible images that made use of gradient residual blocks along with pyramid attention modules. The limitation of the algorithm was the models complexity and computational cost [9]. Shangwang Liu et al. presented an architecture for fusing images that used a combination of BPDB and CBAM in a GAN architecture. The fused images had better edge and texture details but the model was limited to large scale applications [10]. A novel framework combination which included feature extraction and spatial optimization for image fusion was proposed by Duan et al. The framework extracted discriminant features [11]. Zhao and Lu proposed a combined method that used AFOTV model that reduces the effect of noise and retains the important information of the images, this framework performs better than traditional methods [12]. A novel MRI and PET image fusion algorithm that integrates 2D-HT with HIS was proposed by Haddadpour et al. This algorithm preserves both the spatial and spectral information. The effectiveness of the algorithm was accessed by comparing metrics with other algorithms [13]. Inbarani et al. came up with a combination of PSO with RST to perform image fusion, PSO optimised the feature selection while RST preserves relevant features and eliminates redundant features. This method exhibited better classification accuracy and performance than the traditional feature selection methods [14]. A MRI and PET image fusion algorithm for various disease diagnosis was presented by Arash Saboori et al with optimized filter parameters [15]. Emna Brahim et al. proposed a combination of UNet and ResNet for performing extraction and fusion of spectral images, this method outperforms traditional image fusion algorithms and machine learning models but might not be compatible with medical image datasets [25]. Yue Pan et al. presented a deep UNet model that performed multimodal fusion of visual and infrared images which produces fusion results with low noise and distortion but the proposed model fails to fuse all the details from both visual and infrared images [27].

Available literature review on medical image fusion shows a significant development in the field of medical image fusion and the advancements of image fusion in the field of medicine for disease diagnosis and treatment. Conventional techniques such as PCA, IHS, wavelet transforms have been used due to its effectiveness in preserving spectral and spatial information of the images. These conventional methods do not perform effectively when the data is complex and multi-dimensional leading to loss of relevant information.

Current research advancements in machine learning, deep learning shows promising results in the field of medical image fusion which can address the limitations discussed in the literature study. These algorithms help in attaining better fusion of images from various modalities. The literature review details on the gap in the medical image fusion methodologies available and the importance of comparative study between PCA based medical image fusion and CNN based medical image fusion. This work also highlights on the importance of fusion algorithm in the field of medicine for disease diagnosis and treatment planning.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A CT and MRI image fusion algorithm using PCA and CNN with attention mechanism is proposed here. This work aims to produce a CT-MRI fused image that contains information from the CT modality and MRI modality into a single composite image. The proposed method is compared with conventional method through different metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of the algorithm.

For this work paired CT and MRI brain image dataset was used from Kaggle public repository which is divided into training set containing 1700 CT images paired with 1700 MRI images and test set containing

744 CT images paired with 744 MRI images. The CT training images and MRI training images from the training set was used for performing PCA based medical image fusion and CNN based medical image fusion. the CT-MRI image dataset used in the study covered various brain conditions and anatomical structures and hence enhance the accuracy and visualization. The CT-MRI images to be fused are pre-processed, to ensure the dataset is appropriate for using as inputs for the proposed models [16]. The pre-processing steps performed in this work are as follows:

Primarily the source CT images as well as the source MRI images are normalised to a range between [0,1] which ensures all pixels of the input images have equal intensity values. The input source images from different modalities are resized so that all images have same dimensions that allows fusion process to be performed effectively between images of various modalities. Data argumentation is performed on the input images to avoid overfitting and to make the CNN model generalise better when there is an unknown or real-world data.

A. Principal Component Analysis for CT-MRI based Medical Image Fusion

PCA is a dimensionality reduction statistical method popularly used for feature extraction and compression [19]. This method is used for the purpose of image fusion as this algorithm extracts the principal components from multiple image modalities and fuse the relevant features into a single composite image with information from both source images. For this research work CT and MRI brain images are used as the source images and the fused image comprises of complementary features from both CT brain image and input MRI brain images for enhanced diagnosis.

PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion are performed on the pre-processed multimodal source input images. The source images obtained from different modalities contain varied details of the brain structure and are also captured based on various aspects. In general, the CT images contain details of the hard bony structures of the brain whereas the MRI focuses on the soft tissue regions of the brain. This fused CT-MRI image provides both the hard structures as well as the soft tissues in the single image making it easy for clinical applications. The pre-processed source images are flattened into a one-dimensional vector, followed by computation of covariance matrix by PCA decomposition. Covariance matrix identifies the direction of the maximum variance. The principal components are computed from the covariance matrix through the computation of eigen values and eigen vectors. The fused images are generated using the principal components which is the computed from the original images. Normalization is performed on the fused image. Figure 1 represents the block diagram of PCA based CT and MRI image fusion.

The fused images produced by PCA can enhance the visualization of both bone and soft tissue structures in a single image, aiding in comprehensive diagnosis. The fusion process may sometimes blur fine details or introduce artifacts, particularly in regions where the CT and MRI images have significantly different contrasts or structures.

Though PCA is a popular method for image fusion due to its simplicity in dimension reduction, there are a few limitations including loss of low-variance but potentially important features, such as subtle edges or textures that may be clinically relevant in medical images [21]. PCA treats each pixel independently, ignoring spatial relationships between neighbouring pixels. Once the principal components are determined, PCA does not adapt to new data or changes in the image characteristics. This fixed nature can limit its flexibility in dynamic or varied imaging conditions.

Fig. 1. Shows the Flow diagram for multimodal fusion of CT- MRI brain input images using Principal Component Analysis for treatment planning and diagnosis

To overcome the limitations of PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion, we move forward with CT-MRI CNN based medical image fusion. CNNs perform better than conventional fusion algorithms in identifying spatial and spectral details in the medical images. Medical image fusion performed using CNNs integrated with attention mechanisms produce fused images that have the ability to retain important information from both CT and MRI which increases the overall fused image quality for clinical accurate and enhanced diagnosis.

B. CNN for CT-MRI based Medical Image Fusion

Convolutional Neural Networks are widely used deep learning model that have gained popularity in the field of disease detection, disease diagnosis and treatment planning recently [22]. The CNN based medical image fusion models are able to fuse information from unseen datasets and combine features from various imaging modalities including CT, MRI, PET, SPECT etc. For this study, CT images are fused with MRI images. The image fusion process involved in this work includes design of the CNN model, training of the dataset. Equation 1 represents the fusion expression

$$F(i,j) = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N I(i-m, j-n) \cdot K(m,n) + b \quad (1)$$

From equation 1, $I(i,j)$ represent the input image, $K(m,n)$ represents the convolution, b represents bias and $F(i,j)$ shows the output feature map position (i,j) . The pre-processed CT modality images and MRI modality images are given to the input layers of the CNN model. The input images are analysed separately through various convolutional layers. Filtering process is performed in the convolutional layers that identify and extract edge features, texture features and gradient features [18]. The obtained low-level features play a vital role in detecting the important attributes from the respective modalities.

After convolution, a ReLU activation function helps the CNN network to identify complex image patterns. Feature maps obtained from the source CT modality images, MRI modality images after feature extraction is concatenated, to combine the images from different modalities into a single composite fused image. To enhance the model in identifying the most relevant features attention mechanisms are included after the concatenation process. The last layer in the CNN model contains a convolution layer that contains a filter along with a sigmoid activation function. The normalised fused images of range $[0,1]$ are produced in this layer. CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion process is shown in figure 2.

During the CNN model training the parameters are optimized which enables accurate CT- MRI image fusion from the training data set. The input image modalities pairs are divided into batches for the training process. The average squared difference of fused image pixel values to the target image pixel values is termed as the Mean Squared Error, this value helps the model in to train so produce accurate results and minimizing the errors. The weights of the model are adjusted by an Adam optimizer during the training process, the learning rate is fixed to be 0.00, optimiser helps in improving the overall image fusion process after every epoch during the training process. Depending on the resource availability the number of batch sizes are fixed. The loss function is determining the number of epochs.

Fig. 2. Shows the CNN-based image fusion process for CT and MRI images

The CT-MRI fused image obtained are further normalised based on the intensity range to ensure the final fused image intensity is aligned with the intensity ranges of the input CT and MRI images.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fusion results of CT brain images and MRI brain images using PCA and CNN are discussed in this section. Conventional PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion is compared with CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion based on several qualitative and quantitative metrics. For this work a comparative study is presented with the following metrics Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Entropy, and Correlation Coefficient are computed.

A comparative analysis of original CT and MRI images along with PCA fused images and CNN fused images are displayed in figure 3 for 10 cases. In case 1, the PCA fusion results shows that information from

both CT and MRI modalities are integrated along with artifacts which is not present in the CT nor the MRI image. Whereas the CNN fused results have lesser artifacts and smoother. In the next case, the PCA fused image has some distortion though the fusion results highlight necessary features prominently improving the soft tissue contrast, whereas the CNN based fusion preserves the overall contrast of the fused image without inference of artifacts. In case 3, it is noticed that though the PCA fused images contain information from both the image modalities, there is noticeable loss in clarity in the regions with sharp contrast. But when CNN is applied on the images, the fused image seems to be much clearer without distortions.

Fig. 3. Shows the CT images in the first column, MRI images in the second column, CT-MRI image fusion using PCA in the third column, CT-MRI image fusion using CNN in the fourth column.

The case 4 results of PCA fusion as shown in figure 3 works effectively on areas with high contrast but some fine details are lost but both high and low contrast details are preserved better in CNN fusion results. PCA fusion in case 5 as shown in figure 3 clearly shows all the boundaries but some of the CT features are lost. In CNN fusion results the CT and MRI image modalities have been effectively.

The fusion results shown in figure 3 clearly indicate that CNN based medical image fusion has shown reliable results when multi modal images were fused. The convolutional neural networks perform smoother fusion and work effectively in preserving details from both CT and MRI in contrast to the PCA medical image fusion which tends to perform effectively in some situations and tends to introduce artifacts in many cases which could not be reliable for the purpose of clinical diagnosis.

SSIM measures the structural similarity between the fused images and the original CT and MRI images. Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) assesses the clarity of the fused images by comparing the pixel intensity values to those of the original images. Entropy measures the amount of information contained in the fused images [18][20]. Correlation Coefficient assesses the linear relationship between the original and fused images.

TABLE 1: COMPARISON OF QUANTITATIVE METRICS FOR PCA AND CNN- IMAGE FUSION

Metrics	PCA based CT-MRI Image Fusion (Average)	CNN based CT-MRI Image Fusion (Average)
SSIM	0.44	0.96
PSNR(dB)	2.45	37.54
Entropy	-566.1	-1158.6
Correlation Coefficient	-0.49	0.99

The SSIM values for the CNN-based fusion consistently outperformed those for the PCA-based fusion across all cases. The average SSIM value for CNN was 0.96, significantly higher than the PCA's average of 0.44 as shown in Table 1. This indicates that the CNN-based fusion method preserves more structural similarity to the original images, making it more reliable for clinical assessments where accurate representation of both CT and MRI features is crucial. Similarly, the PSNR values demonstrate that the CNN-based fusion results in higher image quality with less distortion or noise. The average PSNR for CNN

was 37.54 dB, compared to 2.45 dB for PCA. The higher PSNR values for CNN indicate better preservation of the original image details, making it a superior method for producing high-quality fused images.

Entropy values provide insight into the information content within the fused images. From Table 1 it can be noted that the average entropy for CNN was -1158.6, compared to -566.1 for PCA. Lower entropy indicates reduction in redundant information and high entropy values in PCA fusion shows the interference of noise in the PCA fused images. Linear relationship between the original and the fused images are represented by the correlation coefficients, with 0.99 average correlation coefficient for CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion and -0.49 for PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion. Higher values of correlation coefficient in CNN based CT-MRI fusion indicates a perfect linear relationship between the fused and original image.

The evaluation metrics shown in Table 1 clearly shows that CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion performs better than PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion. Higher values of SSIM and PSNR in CNN based medical image fusion represent that CNN fusion results are aligned with the original CT and MRI images with respect to quality and structural information details. The redundancy is reduced in CNN based image fusion which can be determined from the entropy values. To conclude with, CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion outperforms PCA based CT-MRI medical image fusion and produces fusion results containing CT and MRI details for clinical diagnosis and treatment planning.

V. CONCLUSION

A comparative analysis on CT-MRI medical image fusion using PCA algorithm and CNN are presented here. The evaluation metrics obtained indicate that CT-MRI image fusion using CNN outperforms the traditional CT-MRI image fusion using PCA. The resultant fused medical images obtained from CNN method consisted of enhanced structural similarity, reduced noise and increased correlations with the input images. The fused images obtained from CNN contained the necessary features that aids in the disease diagnosis for medical practitioners.

Though the study proposes an effective fusion technique to fuse images from different modalities, there are some limitations including the dependency on the available dataset as the CT and MRI images should belong to the same individual and should also be directionally aligned. Moreover, the computational complexity of the CNN model when a diverse data set is used. In the future, deep learning models can be used along with the conventional methods to enhance the features of the fused images. The findings can also be applied on a large/real time dataset to validate and enhance the model. Overall, it can be concluded that CNN based CT-MRI medical image fusion method appears to be much effective in fusing multi modal images.

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